

**CALCULATION OF THE INDICATORS OF THE AXIAL-PISTON HYDRAULIC ENGINE
CORRELATION ANALYSIS**

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ABSTRACT

The absorption of gas (air) into the working fluid at the pump inlet has a significant effect on the volume of the hydraulic motor, that is, it practically reduces it linearly. The load (torque) on the shaft of the hydromotor does not affect the volume of the hydromotor in the investigated limits. Depending on the gas content of the working fluid, the total efficiency of the hydraulic motor practically does not change, except for small loads relative to the pump.

Keywords: Axial-piston pump, engine, correlation analysis, working fluid, hydraulic system.

In the engineering industry, various types of equipment are used in drilling, oil extraction and other fields. Each equipment has its own flaws and shortcomings. However, there are a number of issues that should be considered when applying the equipment. Its main advantages are its small mass and small volume, high frequency and accuracy of reversibility, high efficiency, and high reliability. This article is about an axial-piston pump that has these advantages. This article also provides information on correlation analysis for axial-piston pumps.

The purpose of this article is to provide information about the advantages of axial-piston pumps, to note the indicators of axial-piston pumps for the modern era, and also to note recommendations for future production.

Axial piston pumps are widely used in various fields due to their high efficiency and high pressure. Axial-piston pumps have a working volume of 12...1000 cm³, a pumping pressure of 50 MPa, and an output of 1600 dm³/min at 400...4500 revolutions per minute. Currently, there are various designs of axial-piston pumps. The main feature of axial-piston pumps is that the working cylinders of these pumps are located parallel or at an angle to the rotor axis and have a rotational movement in space.

The increase in the application of axial-piston pumps is due to the high technical and economic indicators. Modern indicators of these pumps: having a high working pressure of 35...50 MPa, a long service life of 10000...12000 hours, a wide rotation frequency range of 2500 revolutions/min, an efficiency coefficient of 97...98%, efficiency 93... reaches 94%, due to its high self-absorption capacity, operation in non-flammable liquids and in open circuits at a rotation frequency of 3000 revolutions/min, low noise level 70...90 dB, due to its high energy characteristics, it can be used in a wide range of output and pressure changes is conveniently used.

Axial-piston pumps and motors compactness, small size, small mass, high pressure, simple adjustment, long service life, high reliability, high efficiency, low noise level, ease of maintenance and universality

of use are favorable for the application of these pumps.

In recent years, many enterprises and factories have been producing axial-piston pumps and engines. For example, OAO «Uralavtoprisep» can be shown. This enterprise produces pumps and motors for construction machinery.

Correlation analysis for axial-piston engines. Correlation analysis allows to clarify the order of dependence between the average value of the studied data (values). It is assumed that the dependence between the studied parameters is linear. The pair coefficients of correlation between parameters of dependence (φ_n and M_m) and hydromotor can be calculated from the following formula:

$$\tau_{xy} = \frac{1}{S_x} \frac{1}{S_y} \sum (x_1 - x)(y_1 - y)$$

where S_x, S_y – variance values for x and y variables; number of even coefficients of variables $n-x$ and y ; The average value of the variables $x, y-x$, and y .

The results of the correlation coefficients between independent (φ_n and M_m) and hydromotor parameters are given in the table. Analysis from this table shows that:

1) There is a negative close relationship between the number of cycles and the air content at the pump inlet (-0.944). However, the relationship between the number of revolutions and the torque on the engine shaft is close to zero. That is, there is no I degree dependence (-123). In addition, there is a high degree of dependence between the number of cycles and the volume of the engine. There is no dependence on the number of cycles and the hydromechanical power of the hydromotor η_{mhm} .

2) The table also shows that the effect of loading on the volume of the hydraulic motor is very small (-0.026). However, the effect of the moment on the hydromechanical efficiency is higher (0.420). From this it can be concluded that the amount of air affects the volume of the hydromotor η_{mh} , but does not affect the hydromechanical η_{mhm} .

Table 1.

Table of pair correlation coefficients for a hydroelectric motor

	p_{mr}	Δp_m	n_m	φ_n	φ_m	M_m	$F\dot{I}\Theta$	$hF\dot{I}\Theta$	$hmex F\dot{I}\Theta$
p_{mr}	1								
Δp_m	0,996	1							
n_m	0,054	-0,017	1						
φ_n	-0,154	0,083	-0,944	1					
φ_m	0,287	0,348	-0,822	0,849	1				
M_m	0,963	0,972	-0,123	0,028	0,475	1			
η	0,276	0,239	0,477	-0,430	-0,171	0,329	1		
η_h	0,124	0,077	0,864	-0,742	-0,626	-0,026	0,507	1	
η_{hmex}	0,254	0,243	-0,027	0,240	0,420	0,420	0,820	-0,073	1

The purpose of preparing this table is to compare the prices of FIA with increasing and decreasing loading. For example, the relationship between the number of cycles and the torque is close to zero. However, there is a high degree of dependence between the number of cycles and the volume of the engine. In the prepared table, the load volume for the engine has a very small effect on the FIA. The torque effect on the hydromechanical FIA is higher. It should be noted here that only linear relationships are determined in correlation analysis. When there are two or more free (independent) variables, for the correlation analysis to be more accurate, it is necessary to determine the special correlation coefficient between the free and the studied parameter.

The specific correlation coefficient is calculated by the following formula based on the obtained correlation tables:

$$r_{xzy} = \frac{r_{xz} - r_{xy}r_{yz}}{\sqrt{1 - r_{xy}^2}\sqrt{1 - r_{yz}^2}}$$

Figure 1.1. The formula for the correlation coefficient

If these points do not line up in a straight line and form a cloud, then the correlation coefficient in absolute value is less than one, and if the cloud is rounded, it approaches zero.

According to this formula, the effect of an independent x change on the z parameter is determined (with the exception of the y change).

The partial to the z parameter of the change y is determined by the following formula:

$$r_{yzy} = \frac{r_{yz} - r_{xy}r_{xz}}{\sqrt{1 - r_{xy}^2}\sqrt{1 - r_{xz}^2}}$$

The free correlation coefficient is taken as a measure of dependence between the studied parameters and free limits:

$$R = \sqrt{\frac{r_{xz}^2 + r_{yz}^2 - 2r_{xy}r_{xz}r_{yz}}{1 - r_{xy}^2}}$$

The value of the correlation coefficient varies between -1 and 1. In the case of full high correlation, this coefficient is +1. For complete negative correlation, it is -1. The straight line passing through the intersection of each pair corresponds to a single line in the graph.

Figure 1.2. The formula for the correlation coefficient

If the correlation coefficient is 0, both variables are completely independent of each other.

If the coefficient is higher than 0.60, the correlation is considered strong: if it is more than 0.90, the correlation is considered very strong. Sample size is of great importance in drawing inferences about relationships between variables. The larger the sample, the more reliable the obtained correlation coefficient.

Results

1. With the increase of gas content and load in the working fluid, the hydromechanical power of the hydromotor increases. The number of cycles of the output point of the hydromotor practically does not depend on the load, but decreases linearly with increasing gas content in the working fluid.

2. In the development and design of axial-piston pumps for the future period, increasing the concentration power in a single unit by increasing the working pressure, increasing the working capacity of the pump

during overloading and during the service period, increasing the efficiency in a wide range of changing working parameters such as efficiency, pressure, and the rotation frequency range recommendations include increasing, reducing the noise and metal capacity of the pump during operation, expanding the working volume in the range of 10...1000 cm³. The most important thing is that the longevity factor is high.

References

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